

Emotional Engagement and Interactive Narrative Design

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Abstract

This paper presents an approach to interactive narrative design that synthesizes the programming capabilities of Macromedia Flash with interface design based on user experience goals to create web-based “storytelling edit systems.” These editing systems allow the user to select and construct an emotionally rich narrative experience from a set of provided data ingredients. In creating such an interactive system, designers must delineate audience engagement in traditional narrative, where the creator has control over all aspects of the story, from interactive narrative, where the designer willingly relinquishes control over narrative development in order to engage its user, providing only the conceptual environment, visual interface and thematically related data ingredients in the form of animated clips that can be manipulated in Flash. This design approach incorporates elements of traditional montage theory as the foundation for transforming data into narrative components that create a unique experience for the user. Through juxtaposition or association, the user assembles these fragments into a conceptual whole, deriving a unique, individual meaning from the narrative sequence they construct. In this interactive paradigm, the designer must link the conceptual environment with a visual interface that contributes to the user’s emotional tone by anticipating their interaction with the project’s elements. This involves connecting the objective realities of the design environment with the subjective realities of the user—their thoughts, memories, and emotions. Metaphor, contrast and repetition provide non-literal alternatives in creating navigational choices that are thematically relevant, aesthetically evocative and tied to those subjective elements that enrich the user experience.

Keywords: Interactive narrative, emotionally driven design, Macromedia Flash, montage theory

Introduction

As digital tools and new venues for distribution transform the ways in which designers can reach their audience, design educators are challenged to present innovative modes of visual communication that prepare students for the full promise of interactive digital design. At the University of Cincinnati, students in my Digital Design III class are creating innovative web-based “storytelling edit systems” in which the user can construct narrative sequences from a set of thematically related data ingredients in the form of animation, video, and audio clips. Their ultimate objective in this process is to design an interactive system that provides an emotionally fulfilling narrative experience for the user. Students examine the issue of user engagement in interactive narrative design and link their concept with design functionality that is grounded in the subjective elements of the user experience rather than simple usability goals. The processes and tools used in the design of these interactive objects are formed around in-class projects that emphasize theoretical principles, design processes, and technical skills. This paper is focused on those classroom explorations.

Traditional and interactive narrative design

Storytelling is one of the oldest experiences and still one of the most powerful because it organizes information in a way that allows us, usually, to draw personal meaning and create knowledge.

Nathan Shedroff, *experience design 1* (2001)

Storytelling as a form of cultural expression has encompassed modes of discourse that range historically from the spoken word to the binary language of the computer age. The emergence of each new medium of communication has spawned innovative approaches to the ways in which information can be organized and presented to its audience. The process of structuring and conveying elements of time, space and the human experience into a series of connected events that engage us emotionally and intellectually has become known as narrative design. Whether printed as text on the pages of a novel or images projected on a screen, traditional narrative design involves its audience through elements of character, plot and conflict that unfold along the trajectory of a dramatic arc that rises from exposition to climax and then resolves.

Traditional narrative in literature and film are comprised of fixed elements stored in finite media that must be experienced in a linear manner in order for the reader/viewer to yield the intended meaning of its creator. The onset of the digital age, with its vast reservoirs of storage media and instantaneous access, is challenging designers of visual communication to once again examine the ways in which stories can be told, and more importantly, experienced by the user. Traditional film design is premised on the assumption of a passive audience who “suspend their disbelief” and accept the filmic construct as a form of reality. Like their cinematic predecessors, interactive narrative is a time-based experience, but by comparison, it provides an environment that is a “time-based representation of character and action in which a reader can affect, choose or change the plot” (Meadows, 2003). In this interactive context the story can change in response to user input, altering its outcome and meaning. This presents a fundamental shift in the role of the designer, as “the goal of an interactive narrative is not to author the narrative, but to provide a context and an environment in which the narrative can be discovered or built by the readers of the story. In this way designers and authors of interactive narrative are far more like architects than writers” (Meadows, 2003). In

a real sense an “interactive narrative” is not a literal narrative at all, but a database of narrative possibilities that exist within the framework of a conceptual interface. In relinquishing control over narrative development, “the user can choose which elements to display or which paths to follow, thus generating a unique work. In this way the user becomes the co-author of the work” (Manovich, 2001). This collaborative environment subverts the passive, voyeuristic role in which audiences experience traditional time-based narrative media. The rational, interactive aspect of choosing and sequencing by the user precludes their suspension of disbelief and requires their active participation. Interactivity “fractures the perspectives of the individual author, places new perspectives in the hands of the readers, and accommodates a relationship between reading and writing” (Meadows, 2003). The deliberate engagement of the user in the narrative process should be linked to the development of a concept that connects the user’s experience and emotional involvement to the project’s data ingredients, navigational activity and project interface.

Database, interface and the user experience

The design process for interactive narrative requires that the creator understands the story as constituent elements of a system rather than a fixed linear narrative. In this context, the designer must first construct a repository for the components that will eventually comprise the narrative experience for the user. This takes the form of a database, which can be viewed as a, “symbolic form of the computer age, a new way to structure our experience of ourselves and of the world” (Manovich, 2001). The database—its buttons, images, text, and sound—are at the heart of the interactive narrative design process, “The narrative is constructed by linking elements of this database in a particular order, that is by designing a trajectory leading from one element to another” (Manovich, 2001). This linking process requires an examination of the issue of datum as narrative ingredient. Each image and sound clip should be viewed as data instead of defined linear narrative components. The user will ultimately choose the order of these individual data ingredients to be played back in the sequence they create. In Digital Design III, students “deconstruct” order to explore unconventional modes of narrative structure whereby the user can become the story editor. Interactive flowcharts, if the piece is simple, provide an overview of the story components as modular design parts and display all possible narrative paths. If the piece is complex, interactive flowcharts show only a few examples of the potential narrative paths the user can construct and then experience.

Montage theory is considered as a foundation for defining when and how datum can become a narrative component instead of mere information. Montage provides the framework for sequences that can develop in a decidedly non-linear manner. As opposed to objective linear narrative development, sequences are now built subjectively by association or by colliding opposing images and/or sounds to create a sense of dialectic, whereby thesis and antithesis are juxtaposed to form a synthesis, or new idea. This juxtaposition of data ingredients can create a “tertium quid,” or third something that is greater than the sum of its parts, allowing the user to derive a new or unexpected meaning. Through this user-initiated process, the narrative outcome is less literal and a more abstract, mood-provoking result can be obtained.

Interface design is a critical aspect of interactive narrative. Students are encouraged to link the story concept with the visual interface so that it is aesthetically evocative, thematically relevant, functional and emotionally engaging. Emphasis is placed on creating an interface that is not a mere container but also a part of the conceptual experience, reinforcing the emotional tone and mood of the story and allowing the user to, “interact with the information in a way that helps us build a personal context and integrate the information into our previous understandings” (Meadows, 2003). The system interface should thematically link to the project’s concept, but its navigational elements should also connect the objective realities of the design environment with the subjective realities of the user—their thoughts, memories, and emotions. The use of visual metaphors can create pictures in the mind of the user “by appealing to people’s perception—sight, sound, touch, and kinesthesia—as well as triggering their memories” (Rogers, Sharp & Preece, 2002). Metaphor, contrast and repetition can all provide non-literal alternatives in creating navigational choices that are tied to those subjective elements that enrich the user experience.

Engaging the user on an emotional level involves an understanding of the relationship between usability and user experience goals in system design. Usability goals are central to functionality. They qualify system interactivity in terms efficiency and its degree of difficulty to learn and remember. User experience goals are less clearly defined and more concerned with the subjective elements of user interactivity such as motivation, conscious and unconscious control, engagement, satisfaction and play aspects. They create the opportunity for an emotionally fulfilling experience by anticipating interaction with the project’s navigational elements and considering what that interaction with the system will feel like to the user. The goals of designing interactive products to be fun, enjoyable, pleasurable and

emotionally pleasing are different from the more objective usability goals “in that they are concerned with how users experience an interactive product from their perspective, rather than assessing how useful or productive a system is from its own perspective” (Rogers, Sharp & Preece, 2002). In balancing elements of usability and the user experience, designers should also consider the emotional involvement and potential of pleasure derived from aspects of play. The user does not necessarily need to completely comprehend the functionality of the system immediately. Although the interactive system should be consistent, not everything has to be user friendly, some functionality can be hidden as the user learns how to use it. The idea of gradually revealing usability allows the user to explore the interface at their own pace, enhancing the individualized experience and adding to a unique sense of narrative development.

Student examples

Once the conceptual framework is in place, students in the Digital Design III class create and edit digital content using a variety of software programs. Students use DV camcorders to shoot video that is captured and edited in Apple’s Final Cut Pro. They create, capture, and edit sound using Digidesign Pro Tools software. Special effect animations are created in Adobe After Effects. This media content is then imported into Macromedia Flash. Each piece of the imported media content is loaded into a movie clip that can be manipulated in Flash through its own programming language called Actionscript. Students create several short animation pieces, either as looped or non-looped movie clips. These clips become the data ingredients the user will use as narrative components in constructing sequences. Users can also apply transitional effects and/or sound effects and music to the sequences they create. Although the experiential environment in which the user constructs the final piece is both non-linear and interactive, once the user has built the sequence and applied effects and sound elements, the outcome is a linear animation that they can watch and then reconstruct if they choose. Reconstruction introduces the idea that altering the sequence can change the outcome and the emotional meaning of both the user’s and the designer’s narrative experience.

Two examples of my students work demonstrate the theoretical, design and technical processes previously discussed in creating “storytelling edit systems” whereby the user creates a variety of emotionally driven interactive narratives.

The first student project, by Matt Broerman, is entitled, “Thoughts” (Figure 1, 2 & 3).

STATE OF NORTH CAROLINA
EVALUATION FOR ADMISSION / CONTINUED STAY
(Restrictive 24-hour Facilities)
Voluntary Minors and Incompetent Adults

County: 10206
Check Number: _____

NAME OF MINOR OR INCOMPETENT ADULT: Alex Winters
ADDRESS (Street, Apt. Number, Box Number, City, State, Zip - Use facility address after 1 year in facility): 1128 Reynolds Street, Westinburg, NC 30205

AGE: 32 BIRTHDATE: 08/12/69 SEX: M RACE: C M.I.: _____
County: _____ Phone: _____

LEGALLY RESPONSIBLE PERSON (Name and Address): _____

Figure 1

SECTION I - CRITERIA FOR COMMITMENT

Inpatient: It is my opinion that the respondent is: mentally ill dangerous to self dangerous to others
(1st Exam - Physician or Psychologist) In addition to being mentally ill it is also mentally retarded
(2nd Exam - Physician only)

Outpatient: It is my opinion that: the respondent is mentally ill the respondent is capable of surviving safely in the community with available supervision
(Physician or Psychologist) based upon the respondent's treatment history, the respondent is in need of treatment in order to prevent further disability or deterioration which would predictably result in dangerousness as defined by G.S. 122C-3 (11)
 the respondent's current mental status or the nature of his illness limits or negates his/her capacity to make an informed decision to seek treatment voluntarily or comply with mandated treatment

Substance Abuse: respondent is: a substance abuser
(1st Exam - Physician or Psychologist) one by Court Order dangerous to himself or others

Clear description of findings: _____
Examination of respondent: _____
Mental and physical status: _____

Figure 2

Figure 3

“Thoughts” tells the fictional story of Alex Winters, a young man who has recently been committed to a mental institution following the divorce of his parents. This expository information is revealed in first-person narration during the Introduction. As we see the State Evaluation for Admission papers layered over a rear view of a human head with an exposed brain, we hear Alex, “These days I just don’t know...I felt forgotten when my parents split

up...” As the Evaluation form is torn away we see photos of Alex and his parents fly over the Criteria for Commitment form with the boxes “Mentally Ill” and “Dangerous to Self” both checked. Alex continues, “My moments of happiness are few and far between...I’ve got so many thoughts just running through my head...” At this point the title is superimposed over the exposed brain and the user can hit the “Enter” button to go to the Main Selection page.

Matt’s concept is to create an experience where the user can select and edit various thoughts and feelings from a database of movie clips to create different thoughts and memories for Alex. The design of the project is anatomical. The interface is centered around Alex’s exposed brain. As the user positions the mouse over various parts of Alex’s brain, memories and feelings such as childhood, love, death, sadness, relaxation, happiness, fear and family appear as designated areas. At the top of the screen, the user is invited to “Drag the Brain to Build Your Thoughts.” When the user drags pieces of a brain into the timeline, they are transformed into movie clips that the user assembles in an order of their choice (Figure 4).

Figure 4

Each clip is made up of images and sounds that help connote the feelings they represent. Each clip reminds us of Alex’s past and perhaps our own. Once the user has drug several clips to the timeline, they are invited to hit the “start thinking” button to display the sequence of memories they have created in the “thought windows” inside the brain (Figure 5). The user can add audio clips to supplement the mood.

Figure 5

Once the user determines the audio that best suits their memories, they can hit the “remember” button to re-experience the set of memories they have created (Figure 6).

Figure 6

Movie clips are kept short and fast, just like fleeting thoughts. All text and headlines are direct references to thinking or the brain (i.e. “lobotomy” deletes all clips from the timeline and returns you to the beginning, “remember” replays the movie). The user can experience the effect of juxtaposition and collision in constructing various sequences. To execute the user’s creation of the “memory” sequence, small examples of all the movie clips are set off-stage. As the user chooses clips, a variable is set (i.e. movieA, movieB). Once the user hits “start thinking,” the correct clip, based off of the previous variable, is duplicated to the stage in the correct position and scale. Once the first clip is done playing (movieA), the frame jumps forward to query the “movieB” variable and determines that movie clip, and so on through “movieE.”

The second student project, by Nick Mitrousis, is entitled, “Synthesis” (Figure 7).

Figure 7

Nick's concept is based on the idea of dialectic montage, whereby thesis and antithesis are juxtaposed to produce a "tertium quid," or third something that cannot be experienced in the individual components. "Synthesis" allows the user to build narrative motion sequences based on movie clips, effects and music clips. The data ingredients are movie clips that have been grouped into two categories, "natural" and "artificial." Both sets of movie clips are kinetic and involve some form of movement within the frame or by the frame of the camera itself. The "natural" clips include gentle waves of water and low-angle tracking shots of a forest. The "artificial clips are of moving subway trains or shots of city traffic at night from the perspective of a moving automobile. The user drags the "natural" and "artificial" clips to the sequence interface, thus creating an animation that has a new meaning, or "synthesis," based on the order they have chosen. Clips can be juxtaposed or layered onto each other in the timeline. The interface for the project is centered on the metaphorical theme of connected molecules, connoting the idea that through the construction of these sequences the user is fusing disparate components and engineering new entities. All text and graphical interface elements have a scientific look. Additional layers of visual effects and sound effects can be applied to the individual or multiple clips in the sequence interface to further alter the meaning (Figure 8 & 9).

Figure 8

Figure 9

Information for the effects is stored in an array structure where each effect is indexed. Array is a high-level programming structure that holds multiple values that are referenced by an indexed number. On the right hand side of the interface are three buttons: transcribe, delete and synthesize. Dragging the data ingredients to the transcribe button allows the user to preview the movie clip. The delete button can be used to remove clips from the timeline. Pressing the synthesize button opens a large viewing molecule that allows the user to watch their narrative sequence as an endless loop (Figure 10). Closing this window takes the user back to the project's interface to build new sequences.

Figure 10

Project outcomes:

During winter and spring quarters of 2003, a group of some thirty Digital Design students were asked to test both interactive projects and provide comments on usability, overall user experience and emotional engagement.

A majority of students cited “Thoughts” for providing a high level of emotional engagement in the overall user experience, noting that the “intro” expository sequence and interface built a strong sense of identification between the character of Alex Winters and the user.

Commenting on the interface, one student noted, “In essence it allows the user to get inside Alex’s head—quite literally.” Other students referred to the database movie clips as a primary agent for building strong emotional engagement, noting the use of “familiar images and sounds, a mother and child, family members at the dinner table, nervous eye movement, a hearse, a gravestone,” in linking to their own set of personal memories and experiences. Many of the students commented on the ease of interactivity and usability in dragging the clips to the nonlinear editing interface “to quickly edit and rearrange sequences in any order.”

The student group gave “Synthesis” high marks for engagement in terms of entertainment, specifically citing the complexity of the interface as vehicle for building a strong element of play, “the interface is functional—it is a nonlinear editing system with clips and a timeline with video and audio tracks—but the visual effects and sound effects tracks made it fun.” Although the students commented positively on their overall user experience, many felt “Synthesis” was lacking in terms of emotional engagement, noting that perhaps it was too “abstract” or “intellectual.” Other students felt that it was lacking a “human element” in its point of view and had “weak narrative development.” Some students found the editing interface to be a little too complex, but most felt that the project was “very intuitive...good organization of database elements and thematic interface made editing easy.”

Conclusion:

History has shown that the art and craft of storytelling has transcended the varying modes and methods through which audiences are emotionally and intellectually engaged. As new media and new digital tools for manipulating new media change, so will the process of organizing

and conveying information to a future audience. Ever-changing culture will inevitably result in ever-changing forms of cultural expression. As this paper has demonstrated, the theories and process involved in designing interactive narrative rely heavily on providing the user in an emotionally fulfilling experience. This will require that digital design practitioners expand their understanding of narrative possibilities in terms of nonlinear development or perhaps non-narrative structure altogether. In allowing the user to construct their own stories, designers must deconstruct order into those data ingredients that will comprise the constituent elements of a system rather than a fixed linear narrative. As interactive narrative becomes more pervasive, designers must focus more precisely on how users experience an interactive product, rather than assessing how useful or productive a system is from its own perspective. Both narrative development and user experience are directly linked to the emotional engagement of the user. In understanding new ways to connect with that future audience—to entertain, to move, to arouse, to educate—designers must search for those subjective, emotional nuances that bind us all. This process will once again find its roots in the classroom as design educators embrace new tools, new paradigms and new pedagogies that foster experimentation and facilitate exploration by the design practitioners of the future into the limitless possibilities for modes of narrative discourse.

REFERENCES

Shredoff, N. 2001. *experience design 1*. Indianapolis, IN: New Riders.

Meadows, M.S. 2003. *Pause & Effect: The Art of Interactive Narrative*. Indianapolis, IN: New Riders.

Manovich, L. 2001. *The Language of New Media*. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.

Rogers, Y., Sharp, H., and Preece, J. 2002. *Interaction Design*. New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.

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